

Binuclear Oxofluoro Complexes of Quinquevalent Molybdenum

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Manuscript received 30 January 1984, revised 7 August 1984, accepted 20 September 1984

The non-electrolytic oxofluoro complexes, $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_2\text{F}_4$ (L = 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) have been prepared from dilute HF medium which hydrolyse to $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_2\text{F}_4$ on digestion with water. All the complexes are very weakly paramagnetic. Ir and the electronic spectra of the complexes confirm the presence of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{4+}$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{3+}$ moiety, respectively.

THE chemistry of quinquevalent molybdenum is dominated by its oxo complexes. The mononuclear paramagnetic complexes containing MoO^{5+} are successively dimerised to diamagnetic or very weakly paramagnetic oxo bridged species $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{4+}$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{3+}$ as the acid concentration is decreased.

A few fluoro complexes containing the moiety $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{2+}$ have already been reported¹⁻³. Only one complex, $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_4$ containing the $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{4+}$ moiety has been reported⁴. The preparation of the complexes containing the $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{4+}$ moiety is somewhat difficult, since the intermediate $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{4+}$ in a reaction may undergo rapid hydrolysis to form $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{3+}$. Previous work in this laboratory showed that adding ligands to $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_5]$ in neutral solution results in the formation of the complexes containing $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{4+}$ moiety directly¹. In the present communication we report the formation of non-electrolytic fluoro complexes of the type $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_2\text{F}_4$ (L = 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) from very dilute HF medium. The properties of these two types of complexes, viz. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_2\text{F}_4$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{L}_2\text{F}_4$, have been compared.

Experimental

$\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_3$ was prepared by standard method⁵. All chemicals used were of E. Merck / B.D.H., G.R./A.R. quality. Molybdenum was analysed by igniting the complexes to MoO_3 . Nitrogen was determined by micro Dumas' method. The method of analysis of fluorine was described earlier⁶.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were taken from the standard sources⁷. Conductance was measured using a Systronics (BPL-India) 303 direct reading conductivity meter. Infrared spectra (KBr/

CsI) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 598 spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra were recorded against MgO with a Carl Zeiss Jena VSU2-P spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out by the method described earlier⁶.

$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_4$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_4$: A solution of 2,2'-dipyridyl (0.95 g, 0.006 mol) or 1,10-phenanthroline monohydrate (1.2 g, 0.006 mol) in HF (40%, 2 ml) was added to a solution of $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_3$ (1.0 g, 0.006 mol) in HF (40%, 3 ml). Ethanol (50 ml) was added to the solution with constant stirring. The deep violet precipitate appeared after 5 min which was separated after 0.5 h, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The yields were about 0.25 g and 0.2 g respectively.

$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_4$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_4$: The compounds $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_4$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_4$ were digested with water for 1 h. The deep violet colour changed to reddish brown. The residues were washed with water and then with ethanol. The yields were almost quantitative.

These two compounds were earlier prepared¹ from $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_5]$. The formation of all the compounds from $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_3$ is shown in Scheme 1. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Compound	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			$\Omega^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$ cm^{2*}	μ_{eff}^{**} B.M.
	Mo	F	N		
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_4$	30.2 (30.5)	12.6 (12.1)	9.2 (8.9)	9	0.65
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_4$	28.2 (28.4)	10.8 (11.2)	8.4 (8.2)	9	0.69
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_2$	31.2 (31.6)	6.0 (6.3)	9.1 (9.2)	8	0.28
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_2$	29.1 (29.3)	5.7 (5.8)	8.4 (8.6)	5	0.15

* $10^{-3} M$ dimethyl sulphoxide solution (dipy)₂F₂ (methanolic solution) at 25°.

** Per molybdenum atom at 27°.

band at 765 and 770 cm^{-1} in the spectra of both the complexes containing this ligand. The assignment of a second band characteristic of a MoO_2Mo or MoOMo group⁹ in the lower frequency region is difficult because of the occurrence of Mo-F bands in this region.

The electronic spectra of the complexes containing the $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4^{2+}$ moiety give bands in the regions of about 32000 and 22000 cm^{-1} (Table 3). The complexes containing the $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{3+}$ unit, however, show strong absorption bands (in addition to those given by the complexes containing $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4^{2+}$ unit) in the lower region, *i.e.* 17000 and 13000 cm^{-1} . These spectral characteristics are quite in accordance with other similar complexes¹⁰ of molybdenum.

 TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm^{-1})

Compound	$\nu_{\text{Mo-O}_2}$	$\nu_{\text{MoO}_2\text{Mo/MoOMo}}$	Other bands
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_4$	950 vs, 960 s	730 s	3420 m, 3110 w, 3075 w, 2920 vw, 2825 vw, 1595 s, 1570 vw, 1490 vw, 1470 m, 1440 vs, 1380 vw, 1315 m, 1160 vw, 1025 m, 930 m, 910 m, 790 s, 770 vs, 655 vw, 635 vw, 570 s, 550 s, 525 m, 505 s, 420 vw, 365 vw.
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_4$	950 vs, 925 s	735 s, 725 vs	3420 m, 3050 w, 2920 vw, 1620 w, 1600 vw, 1575 w, 1515 m, 1490 vw, 1425 vs, 1380 vw, 1340 vw, 1220 vw, 1140 vw, 1105 vw, 895 w, 870 m, 850 vs, 780 m, 650 w, 570 m, 555 w, 500 m, 485 w, 425 w, 370 vw.
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_2$	950 vs	735 vs	3410 s, 3050 m, 1590 m, 1460 m, 1430 s, 1308 m, 1275 w, 1240 w, 1220 w, 1155 m, 1100 w, 1055 w, 1025 m, 875 m, 800 m, 765 vs, 650 m, 635 m, 605 m, 490 m.
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_2$	955 vs	730 s	3470 m, 3050 w, 1600 w, 1575 w, 1510 w, 1490 w, 1420 m, 1335 w, 1300 w, 1220 w, 1140 w, 1105 w, 870 m, 850 s, 790 m, 640 m, 608 m, 500 m, 470 m, 420 w.

Results and Discussion

Both the complexes containing $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{3+}$ are deep violet in colour and are insoluble in water and other common organic solvents except having a low solubility in acetone and dimethyl sulphoxide. The complexes containing the moiety $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4^{2+}$ are reddish brown in colour. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_2$ is feebly soluble in water, methanol and ethanol, while $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_2$ is moderately soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. The low molar conductances of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions in dimethyl sulphoxide (methanol in the case $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_2$) show the nonelectrolytic behaviour of the complexes (Table 1). As expected, all the complexes are very weakly paramagnetic, μ_{eff} varying from 0.15 to 0.69 B.M. (Table 1) at 27°.

The ir spectra of all the complexes (Table 2) show intense terminal $\nu_{\text{Mo-O}_2}$ stretches around 950 cm^{-1} . There is no ligand absorption in this range. Strong absorptions around 730 cm^{-1} may be safely assigned to bridging MoO_2Mo or MoOMo vibrations, since 1,10-phenanthroline does not absorb strongly in this region. 2,2'-Dipyridyl gives a strong band⁸ at 755 cm^{-1} , which is observed as a separate

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	$\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_4$	34500 m, 23200 vs, 16600 vs, 13300 vs
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_4$	32200 m, 23500 vs, 17200 vs, 13200 m
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{dipy})_2\text{F}_2$	33300, 22000
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{phen})_2\text{F}_2$	32200, 22000

The thermogram of the complexes showed that they begin to decompose very slowly from about 60° and the decomposition is very rapid from about 240° and finally at 470-550° they form MoO_3 .

References

- M. C. CHAKRAVORTI and A. K. BERA, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1983, 8, 83.
- R. MATTES and G. LUX, *Angew. Chem.*, 1974, 86, 598.
- R. MATTES, K. MENNEMANN, H. RIESKAMP and H. BROCKMEYER, *J. Less-Common Met.*, 1980, 76, 199.
- R. KERGOAT and J. E. GUERCHAIS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1972, 1746.
- W. G. PALMER, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", University Press, Cambridge, 1954, p. 406.
- M. C. CHAKRAVORTI and S. C. PANDIT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 3644.
- J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1960, p. 403.
- R. J. H. CLARK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1377.
- E. I. STIEFEL, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 22, 85.
- E. I. STIEFEL, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 22, 77.